

RELIABILITY OF COMPOSITE TIDAL TURBINE BLADES

M.Arhan¹, P.Davies¹, S.Paboeuf², and E. Nicolas³

¹ Marine Structures Laboratory, Ifremer Brittany Centre, Plouzané, France, peter.davies@ifremer.fr, mael.arhan@ifremer.fr, www.ifremer.fr

² Bureau Veritas Marine & Offshore, Nantes, France, stephane.paboeuf@bureauveritas.com, www.bureauveritas.com

³ Sabella SAS, Quimper, France, e.nicolas@sabella.bzh

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes early results from the Realtide H2020 European project which aims to improve the reliability of tidal turbines to generate renewable marine energy. The composite blades are a critical component and a testing campaign has been performed to investigate their long term durability. Results are shown for seawater aging and its influence on fatigue performance. These results will be integrated into models of long term behaviour.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fibre reinforced composites are being used for most of the blades of tidal turbines currently being developed [1,2]. These structures, up to ten meters long, are subjected to high cyclic loads while immersed in seawater. Although composites have been used for marine structures for many years, these loading conditions, with strong water/mechanical load coupling, have not been studied in detail. Fig. 1 shows an example, the Sabella D10 turbine (diameter: 10 meters), installed in the Fromveur strait off the Brittany coast, and is the first ocean energy system grid connected in France.

Figure 1: Sabella tidal turbine during installation

Long-term reliability is critical to the commercial success of these marine energy recovery systems, and must be fully understood. This is one of the aims of the H2020 project RealTide, Grant Agreement n°727689 (Advanced monitoring, simulation and control of tidal devices in unsteady, highly turbulent realistic tide environments) [3]. Project partners are Bureau Veritas (coordinator), Bureau Veritas Marine & Offshore Solutions, the University of Edinburgh, EnerOcean, IngeTeam, 1-Tech, Sabella and Ifremer. The project is addressing the factors that contribute to reliability, and integrating them in a quantitative tide-to-wire model; these include the ocean energy resource, hydrodynamics, mechanical behavior, and electrical energy generation. A main focus of the project is to propose a methodology to properly design a tidal turbine blade, based on realistic loadings. To do

so, the project uses results from the D10 tidal turbine development stages, which is summarized in the flowchart shown in Fig. 2. Moreover, Sabella is now working on a new and bigger turbine, called the D12, which will have a total diameter of 12 meters. This same turbine was chosen as a study case for the project and the development methodology is similar to that of the D10 presented in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Flowchart of the previous Sabella D10 project and development towards the D12 tidal turbine within the Realtide project

The main focus of this paper is to investigate the effect of sea water aging on the static and fatigue properties of infused composite material and its effect on blade design. First, some results from the previous D10 study will be presented. Samples from this study have been immersed in sea water for more than six years. Second, results obtained within the Realtide project will be presented and will be used to design the Sabella D12 tidal turbine.

2 MATERIALS & METHODS

2.1 Materials

Two similar carbon/epoxy materials are discussed in this paper, the one from the D10 study and the one investigated within the Realtide project, i.e. for the D12 tidal turbine. The characteristics of the materials are shown in Table 1. These were both manufactured using resin infusion and T700 carbon fibres. The resin was supplied by Sicomin and is a high performance epoxy resin for infusion. Two different hardeners were used: SD8824 and SD8823. Only the hardener is changed in these two materials, but this has an effect on the glass transition temperature. To enhance understanding, the neat resin from the D12 study was also investigated.

Study	Resin	Hardener	Fiber Weight (g/m ²)	Sequence	Thickness (mm)	T _g (°C)
D10	SR1710	SD8824	600	[0] _{2s}	2	79
D12	SR1710	SD8823	600	[0] _{2s} [± 45] _s [0/ ± 45] _s	2	102

Table 1: Characteristics of the Carbon/Epoxy materials used in this paper

2.2 Mechanical tests

Static tests

Tensile tests were performed on composite materials according to ISO 527 on an Instron™ testing machine using a load cell of 200 kN at a crosshead speed of 2 mm/min. These were carried out on three different sequences: [0°], [90°] and [$\pm 45^\circ$]. All the specimens were tabbed using glass/epoxy tabs with a sequence of [$\pm 45^\circ$]. For each condition, five specimens were tested. Strain was measured using two different methods: a mechanical extensometer with a gauge length of 50 mm to measure strain in the longitudinal direction and a Digital Image Correlation system (DIC) to measure strain in the longitudinal and transverse direction.

These tests provide values of E_1 , E_2 , ν_{12} and G_{12} , together with σ_1 , σ_2 and τ_{12} . Modulus values were calculated as the slopes of the stress-strain plots over the strain range 0.1-0.3%. Stress for the tests on unidirectional materials was taken as $\sigma = \frac{L}{S}$. For the tests on specimens at [$\pm 45^\circ$] stress was taken as $\tau_{12} = \frac{\sigma_{12}}{2.5}$. Shear strain was taken as $\gamma_{12} = \epsilon_y - \epsilon_x$.

Tensile tests were also performed on the neat resin at a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min on an Instron™ testing machine with a load cell of 10 kN.

Interlaminar shear strength tests were performed on unidirectional 0° specimens, according to ISO 14 130 (support length/thickness = 5) on an Instron™ testing machine using a 10 kN load cell. These were performed at a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min until delamination occurred. For each condition, five specimens were tested to failure. The apparent Interlaminar Shear Strength τ_{13} was measured using the following equation:

$$\tau = \frac{3}{4} \times \frac{F}{bh}$$

Where F is the load in N. b and h are respectively the width and the thickness of the specimen.

Fatigue tests

Fatigue tests were performed on a 25 kN Zwick hydraulic test frame for four point flexure (120 × 25 mm²) specimens with 50 mm between upper loading points and 100 mm between lower supports. Tests were performed at a frequency of 2 Hz using an R-ratio of 0.1. All flexural tests were performed immersed in continuously renewed seawater at 25°C.

2.3 Sea water aging

The water absorption was determined from the weight change measurements of square samples (50 x 50 x thickness mm³) at 60°C. The samples have been immersed in natural renewed sea water from Brest Estuary. The tanks are shown in Fig.3. The mass gain was followed by periodic weighing of the different specimens on a Sartorius LA310 S balance having a precision of 0.1 mg. Before each measurement in immersion, the water on the surface of the specimen was wiped off with a paper towel. For each measurement, three samples were weighed at each time. The water content, M(t) in wt.% of a sample is defined as follows:

$$M(t) = \frac{m(t) - m_0}{m_0} \cdot 100$$

Where $m(t)$ is the mass of the sample at a time t and m_0 the initial mass of the sample.

Figure 3: Sea water aging test tanks

All the specimens used for mechanical characterization have been immersed in sea water at 60°C.

3 SOME RESULTS FROM THE SABELLA D10

Results from sea water aging tests performed within the Sabella D10 study are presented in this section. Quasi-unidirectional interlaminar shear strength specimens have been immersed in the sea water tanks at Ifremer for more than 6 years. Examples of results are shown in Fig.4.

Figure 4: Effect of sea water aging at 60°C on the Interlaminar shear strength

Fig.4 shows that the interlaminar shear strength drops from 62 MPa down to 50 MPa after two months of immersion, a decrease of about 20%. This corresponds to the point where the $[0]_{2s}$ composite reaches sea water saturation. Afterwards, only an additional 5% decrease occurs after 6 years of aging, so a 25% decrease in total, which shows that this infused carbon/epoxy (T700/SR1710) composite is a promising candidate for such applications.

4 RESULTS FROM THE SABELLA D12 - REALTIDE

The results presented in section 3 represent a rare result in the aging community. Very few studies show results after six years of sea water aging at different water temperatures. However, these results can hardly be used in design. This is one of the reasons why additional aging studies were started within the Realtide project, in order to design a turbine blade using the aged data. To do so, a significant number of specimens were immersed in sea water at 60°C. These include the neat resin as well as composite materials with different sequences: $[0]_{2s}$, $[90]_{2s}$, $[\pm 45]_s$ and $[0/\pm 45]_s$. First, results from weight gain coupons are presented. Second, the effect of sea water aging on the mechanical properties in static and fatigue loading are presented.

4.1 Water uptake

Results from water uptake tests are presented in this section. Fig.5. shows the change in weight gain as a function of time for the neat resin (Fig.5.a) and for two different composite sequences (Fig.5.b).

Figure 5: Weight gain for coupons immersed at 60°C (a) Neat resin – Two different thicknesses (b) Composite – $[0]_{2s}$ and $[\pm 45]_s$ sequences

Results from Fig.5.a show the change in weight induced by water upon aging at 60°C in sea water. Coupons with two different thicknesses were used here, in order to check whether or not the water diffusion may be modelled using a Fickian law. For further information concerning the Fickian law, the reader is invited to check these two references [4, 5]. Results show that all the coupons absorb the same amount of water, i.e 3.2%. Moreover, the water diffusion can be modelled using a Fickian law in both cases, using the exact same parameters (diffusion coefficient and mass at saturation). Therefore, the water diffusion within the resin is considered Fickian.

Then, results from Fig.5.b show the change in weight induced by water for two carbon/epoxy sequences $[0]_{2s}$ and $[\pm 45]_s$ using the same resin as that of Fig.5.a. In these two cases, the $[0]_{2s}$ and $[\pm 45]_s$ absorb respectively 0.93 and 1.15 % of water. If we take into account the fibre weight content in the calculations ($M_{f[0]} = 70.3\%$, $M_{f[\pm 45]} = 61.8\%$), this corresponds to 3.13 and 3.0% of water within

the resin itself, which corresponds to the water content at saturation obtained on the neat resin to a first approximation. These results confirm that the panels are of a very good quality in terms of voids. However, the water diffusion within the composites cannot be modelled using a Fickian law, despite the fact that this works for the resin. Further work is needed to model the water diffusion within these two composite laminates.

4.2 Effect of sea water aging on the static mechanical properties

Along with the weight gain coupons, tensile specimens (neat resin and different composite sequences) were immersed at 60°C for mechanical characterization. After reaching saturation, these were tested to failure following the method described in section 2.2. Stress-Strain plots are shown in Fig. 6 and results are summarized in Table 2.

Figure 6: Results from tensile tests - Stress-strain plots after aging at 60°C (a) [0]_{2s}, (b) [90]_{2s}, (c) [±45]_s (d) Neat resin

State	Unaged	Saturated in Sea Water at 60°C	Change in property (%)
E_1 (GPa)	120.3 ± 2.1	121.1 ± 3.6	+1
E_2 (GPa)	9.4 ± 0.3	9.4 ± 0.5	0
G_{12} (GPa)	4.5 ± 0.4	3.4 ± 0.1	-24
ν_{12}	0.26 ± 0.02	0.25 ± 0.05	-4
σ_1 (MPa)	2285 ± 102	2083 ± 248	-9
σ_2 (MPa)	46 ± 2	20 ± 2	-57
τ_{12} (MPa)	73 ± 7	63 ± 2	-14
τ_{13} (MPa)	72 ± 2	59 ± 2	-18
E_{resin} (GPa)	3.6 ± 0.1	2.8 ± 0.1	-22
σ_{resin} (MPa)	92 ± 1	78 ± 2	-15
ϵ_{resin} (%)	6.0 ± 0.2	4.6 ± 1.3	-23

Table 2: Effect of sea water aging on the static mechanical properties of T700/SR1710 composites

From all the results shown in Fig.6 and summarized in Table 2, two main aspects can be highlighted. On one hand, the mechanical properties highly dominated by the fibre behaviour such as E_1 and σ_1 are not affected after water aging. On the other hand, all the mechanical properties highly matrix or interface dominated are affected by water. The property most affected by water is the transverse tensile strength σ_2 , which decreases by more than 50%, unlike other properties such as G_{12} , τ_{12} , E_{resin} and σ_{resin} , which decrease by about 20%. While the latter may be associated with plasticization of the resin, the decrease observed on the transverse tensile strength may be associated with an interface degradation. To valid this assumption, neat resin and composite specimens are currently being dried, to investigate if the loss in mechanical properties is reversible. Results from this drying stage will be presented at the conference.

It may be noted that the unaged results have already been used to design the D12 blades by Sabella, and one blade will be manufactured in 2019 and tested at Ifremer on a specific test bench. Also, another task includes the use of the aged mechanical properties in design, i.e. to use the degraded properties in the same numerical models as those used to design the composite in the unaged state. This will allow us to conclude on the consequences of designing a blade using the aged mechanical properties rather than the unaged properties.

4.3 Effect of sea water aging on the fatigue mechanical properties

Although static mechanical characterization in the aged state is of interest, a turbine blade during use is subjected to flexural fatigue loadings. This is one of the reasons why four point flexural fatigue tests were performed within the RealTide project on composite sequences likely to be used in design such as $[0/90]_s$ and $[0/\pm 45]_s$, before and after sea water aging. It may be noted that the static flexural strength for the $[0/\pm 45]_s$ sequence drops by about 20% after aging (1118 ± 55 MPa in the unaged state and 879 ± 60 MPa after sea water aging). Flexure is a highly resin and interface dominated test, which is why the drop observed here correlates well with the tensile results after aging from section 4.2. Then, results from flexural fatigue tests before and after sea water aging are shown in Fig.7. The maximum flexural stress during test is shown as a function of number of cycles to failure in Fig.7.a. The normalized stress (either in the unaged or aged state) is presented as a function of the number of cycles to failure in Fig.7.b.

Figure 7: (a) Flexural fatigue tests results before and after aging (b) Normalized stress (maximum applied stress/flexural strength in static in the unaged or aged state) as a function of number of cycles to failure

First, results from Fig.7.a show that sea water aging has a clear effect on the flexural fatigue life of [0/45]_s laminates. However, results from Fig.7.b tend to show that the decrease in fatigue lifetime in the aged state is mostly due to a shift in the S-N curve induced by the 20% drop in static flexural strength. Indeed, the slope of the normalized S-N curve after sea water aging is very similar to that in the unaged state. Additional tests will be performed to complete the S-N curve and flexural fatigue tests will be performed on aged [0/90]_s laminates.

Finally, tensile fatigue tests in water will also be performed within the project on [0/±45]_s and [0/90]_s laminates before and after sea water aging. Moreover, for some laminates, the effect of R-ratio on the fatigue lifetime will be investigated. The aim of this is to try to reproduce and adapt the methodology used in the OPTIMAT BLADES project [6] to design reliable wind turbine blades. Indeed, large databases now exist for wind turbines [7, 8]. Another aspect that will be investigated concerns fatigue tests using variable amplitude loading, based on results which have been obtained from the instrumentation (strain gauges) of the Sabella D10 prototype during sea trials. Examples of these results will be presented at the conference. The loadings can vary considerably, not only between sites but also within a given site, so specific flow measurements are required [9], and these are being installed.

5 CERTIFICATION APPROACH

For a Classification Society in charge of the certification, as described in [10], it is important to be confident in the values used for the design review of an innovative system such as a tidal turbine and especially for the design assessment of blades. Indeed, the reliability of the system is mainly based on the reliability of blades and so, the coupling effect of cycling loads and seawater on the mechanical properties of composite materials are to be considered. As little feedback exists and even less standards for this application, such research results are very useful for the validation and calibration of safety factors.

In the guidance note NI 603 Current and Tidal Turbines [11], Bureau Veritas defined the safety factors to be considered for composite materials blade. The safety factors (SF) are calculated from a combination of partial safety factors as below:

$$SF = \alpha C_v C_F C_R C_L$$

With:

- α , a basic allowable stress factor to consider the loading type: normal, extreme, testing or accidental;
- C_V , a partial safety factor taking into account the ageing effect;
- C_F , a partial safety factor taking into account the fabrication process and the reproducibility of the fabrication;
- C_R , a partial safety factor taking into account the type of load carried out by the fibres of the reinforcement and the core;
- C_L , a partial safety factor taking into account the type of analysis.

The partial safety factor C_V concerning the ageing is to be taken equal to:

- 1.35 for monolithic laminates and face-skins laminates of sandwich;
- 1.25 for sandwich core materials.

The early results obtained by Ifremer in the Realtide project seem to confirm the order of magnitude of values considered in the note NI603 for the ageing effect. However, further tests will allow us to complete our knowledge on the durability and to improve requirements and methodology for the design assessment of tidal turbine blades. The objective is to reduce as much as possible the partial safety factor C_V or to adapt it depending on the ageing test results.

6 CONCLUSIONS

Composite blades are a critical element in improving reliability of tidal turbines.

Results from a first aging study on the Sabella D10 turbine were presented and have shown that carbon/epoxy (T700/SR1710) is a suitable candidate for such applications. Indeed, the interlaminar shear strength of unidirectional laminates only decreased by 25% after 6 years of immersion in sea water at 60°C.

In order to investigate long term durability in more detail, resin and composite specimens with different stacking sequences were immersed in sea water at 60°C until water saturation and tested both under static and fatigue loading. Results have shown that the matrix and interface dominated properties decrease by about 20-25% after aging. This drop shows that it is essential to take aging into account when designing a tidal turbine.

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